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CHALLENGES FACING SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to ascertain the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria. The study used survey research design to gather data from two hundred respondents from small and medium in Abuja. The study employed t-test statistical technique to ascertain the extent to which these challenges hamper the growth of SMEs. The results showed that tax multiple taxation, access to finance and power supply are the major challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria. The results also showed that power supply is the 1st ranked challenge while multiple taxation is the ranked the least challenge facing SMEs in Nigeria. This study recommended that commercial banks should reduce credit requirements for SMEs.

Keyword: power supply, multiple taxation, access to finance

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In recent times the world economy has developed tremendously and this development can be attributed to activities of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), especially in developing countries of world (Ariyo, 2005). Basil (2001) reports that the roles played by small and medium scale enterprises in communal and economic development cannot be overestimated. The author further documents that SMEs sector is the highest employer of labour and it contributes immensely to the GDP of any meaningful economy. Ariyo (2005) opines that SMEs is a vehicle used for accomplishing sustainable growth. To assume this important role SMEs must marshal out strategies that will enable them overcome a number of key business challenges that confront them on daily basis. Some of these challenges include, high production costs, low employee productivity and inability to build competitive advantage through producing quality products and services and low entrepreneurial interventions (UNCTAD, 2005). However anecdotal evidence shows that SMEs in developing countries like Nigeria are faced with a lot of challenges that have hampered their growth in recent times. Among these challenges are: intermittent power supply, indiscriminate tax levies, low accessibility to loans from financial institutions and inability to keep proper financial records. Oluboba (2010) reports that the main problems facing SMEs, which are however not unsurmountable are: low level of entrepreneurial skills, poor management practices, low access to money and capital markets, low equity participation from the promoters because of insufficient personal savings due to their level of poverty and low return on investment, inadequate equity capital, poor infrastructural facilities, high rate of enterprise mortality, shortages of skilled manpower, multiplicity of regulatory agencies and overbearing operating environment, societal and attitudinal problems, integrity and transparency problems, restricted market access, lack of skills in international trade; bureaucracy, lack of access to information given that it is costly, time consuming and complicated at times. In the same vein Onugu (2010) reports that the major challenges facing SMEs include; insufficient capital, lack of focus, inadequate market research, over-concentration on one or two markets for finished products, lack of succession plan, inexperience, lack of proper book keeping, lack of proper records or lack of any records at all, inability to separate business and family or personal finances, lack of business strategy, inability to distinguish between revenue and profit, inability to procure the right plant and machinery, inability to engage or employ the right caliber of staff, painlessness, cut-throat competition, lack of official patronage of locally produced goods and

services, dumping of foreign goods and over-concentration of decision making on one (key) person, usually the owner. Other challenges which SMEs face in Nigeria include irregular power supply and other infrastructural inadequacies. unfavourable fiscal policies, multiple taxes, levies and rates, fuel crises or shortage, policy inconsistencies, reversals and shocks, uneasy access to funding, poor policy implementation, restricted market access, raw materials sourcing problems, competition with cheaper imported products, problems of inter-sectorial linkages given that most large scale firms source some of their raw material outside instead of sub-contracting to SMEs, insecurity of people and property, fragile ownership base, lack of requisite skill and experience, thin management, unfavourable monetary policies, lack of preservation, processing and storage technology and facilities, lack of entrepreneurial spirit, poor capital structuring as well as poor management of financial, human and other resources.

Osoba (1987) and Innag and Ukpong (1993) opine that financial institutions classify loans disbursed to small and medium scale enterprises as “high risk loans”. They are accorded low priorities in the lending schemes especially by the commercial banks. The financial institutions also claim that the owners of these enterprises most of the time are unable to provide required collateral securities and are also unable to cope with the high interest on loan charged by commercial banks. SMEs are unable to raise funds in the capital market either because they cannot fulfill the conditions, or because they are ignorant of the facilities provided by the market. As a result of the foregoing, SMEs in general and the SSEs in particular find it difficult to expand their business operations.

Olayemi (2012) stresses that the importance of electricity supply to the growth of SMEs and industrialization cannot be overemphasized. The author opines that the current unemployment rate is close to forty per cent and industrial capacity utilization that is below thirty per cent are major problems caused by the epileptic electricity supply. He stresses that the shortage of power supply in Nigeria has gained rapt attention of indigenous researchers because of the adverse effect it has on industrialization. Kim (1997) also reports that shortage of power supply is the major factor that grounded many businesses in Nigeria. Some businesses have to shift their base to neighboring African countries like Ghana and Benin Republic because of epileptic electricity supply in Nigeria. China in its own wisdom leverage on this shortcoming and use Nigeria as dumping ground for generators. Most Nigerians believe that the importers of generators will do all within their power to make sure that poor electricity supply is not rectified because if it is rectified they will be out of business (Arowolo, 2012). Dismal state of infrastructure, with particular reference to power supply, transportation and workspace led to low productivity and stunted growth of SMEs.

Holtz-Eakin (1995) document that in levying SMEs, tax ought to be done in such a way that it will put the income size and need for survival into consideration. It is expedient that enough profit is allowance is given to them for the purpose of business expansion. Some scholars suggest that tax policy must be not gear toward encouraging SMEs to remain in the informal sector or to evade or avoid tax payments. Other scholars argued that many small firms in Africa, including Nigeria, choose to remain in the informal sector because of the perceived benefits derived from remaining in the informal sector outweigh the perceived costs.

Stem and Barbour (2005) argue that for SMEs to grow, the tax rates must be realistic and not to asphyxiate the businesses of their working capital. Holtz-Eakin (1995) argues there is no economic legal clause that is enunciated to give the preferential treatment to SMEs with regard to tax. Some of the factors that could be advanced in favour tax concessions for SMEs includes: the presence of externalities provided by small firms that benefit the economy, the rewards for which are not fully captured by small firms, for example, there is a need for government to provide tax- break for small firms, on the basis of equity and the tax system should not be designed to affect the growth of the SME's in a negative way.

The object of this study is ascertain the challenges facing SMEs. This study is different from previous studies because it focuses on the challenges posed on SMEs with regard to taxation, power supply and access to funds. The study was restricted to some selected medium scale manufacturing businesses in Nigeria.

Objective of the study

This broad objective of this study to ascertain the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria while the specific objectives are to:

1. ascertain the relationship between multiple tax and growth of SMEs in Nigeria
2. find out the relationship between power supply and growth of SMEs in Nigeria

3. instigate the relationship between access to fund and growth of SMEs in Nigeria

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Small and medium scale enterprises

The definition of SMEs depends mainly on the level of development of the country. In most developed market economies like the United States of America (USA), U.K. and Canada the definition criterion adopted a mixture of annual turnover and employment levels. In Nigeria, the Small and Medium Industries Enterprises Investment Scheme (SMIEIS) defines SME as any enterprises with a maximum asset based of N200 million excluding land and working capital and with a number of staff employed not less than 10 or more than 300.

In extant literature small and medium scale enterprises are usually determined by various quantitative parameters. Such parameters include the number of people employed in the enterprises, the capital investment outlay, the size of the plant capacity, the sophistication of the equipment, sales turnover, and profit margin and perhaps market share. In Nigeria, existing official definitions, by government agencies such as the Federal Ministry of Industries, Central Bank of Nigeria emphasize nominal financial outlay as the operational indices for defining small and medium scale enterprises. The current national definition of SMEs in Nigeria as adopted at the National Council on Industry (NCI) in 1996 and as cited by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 1997) is to classify small scale enterprises as those with total cost, including working capital but excluding cost of land above N1.0 million, but not exceeding N 40.0 million with a labour size of between 11 and 35 workers. Medium Scale Enterprises are defined as those with total cost, including capital but excluding cost of land above N40.0 million but not exceeding N150.0 million with a labour size of between 36 and 100 workers. In this study however, the use of qualitative criteria in defining small and medium scale enterprises is preferred. This definitional preference is based on the realization of the ever-changing quantitative economic indicators affecting money both as a unit of account and as a store of value. These indicators include interest rates, the level of prices and exchange rates. Against this background and according to Koroma (1992) small and medium scale enterprises may be seen to exhibit the following characteristics.

Tax policy and SMEs

Tomlin (2008) documents that economists barney is that the amount expended by smaller companies on tax may well be used for reinvestment that could aid future growth. He further contends that taxes and complex tax system put disproportionate pressure on smaller businesses. Some schools of thought are of the opinion that low income taxpayers under the regular system of taxation are disadvantaged due to fact that the compliance requirements, cost of compliance and tax rate are the same for both small and large enterprises. SMEs usually have to operate under an overbearing regulatory environment with plethora of regulatory agencies, multiple taxes, cumbersome importation procedure and high port charges that constantly exert serious burden on their operations. Many SMEs have to deal with myriad of agencies at great cost because they are heterogeneous and these differences in size and structure may in turn carry differing obligations for record-keeping that affect the costs of the enterprises complying with (and to the revenue authorities of administering) alternative possible tax obligations. Public corporations, for example, commonly have stronger accounting requirements than sole proprietorships, and enterprises with employees may be subject to the full panoply of requirements associated with withholding labour income taxes and social contributions (International Tax Dialogue 2007). An overly complex regulatory system and tax regime or one opaque in its administration and enforcement make tax compliance unduly burdensome and often have a distortion effect on the development of SMEs as they are tempted to morph into forms that offer a lower tax burden or no tax burden at all (Masato, 2009) and this results in a tax system that imposes high expenses on the society. A poorly executed tax system also leads to low efficiency, high collection charges, waste of time for taxpayers and the staff, and the low amounts of received taxes and the deviation of optimum allocation of resources (Farzod, 2000). Existing empirical evidence clearly indicates that small and medium sized businesses are affected disproportionately by these costs: when scaled by sales or assets, the compliance costs of SMEs are higher than for large businesses (Weichenrieder, 2007). Among the factors militating against SME tax compliance with are: high tax rates, Low efficiency, high collection charges, waste of time for taxpayers and the staff, and the low amounts of received taxes and the deviation of optimum allocation of resources (Farzod, 2000). Yaobin, (2007) opines other factors that lead to

low tax compliance by SMEs are double taxation, no professional tax consultancy, weak tax planning, high taxation cost.

Power Supply and Small and Medium Scale Enterprises

Some scholars argued that unemployment has a direct link with powersupply. Intermittent power supply has made many businesses in developing nations to die prematurely. Ayodele (2001) argues that the development of the Nigerianeconomy as an emerging market is technically a function of amount electricity powerthat it can generate. Similarly, Okafor (2008) argues that poor power generation epitomizes a fundamental industrial setback for the Nigerian economy. Asaolu and Oladele (2006) argue that infrastructural decadence is the major problemconfronting Nigeria and that electricity generation is one of the examples of the infrastructural deterioration in Nigeria. In the same vein, Rabi (2009) posits that for three epochs, inadequate quantity, quality and access toelectricity supply remain a big challenge to the Nigerian economy. The author further reports that the resolution of this challenge wouldboost the economy, reduce unemployment and the resultant social vices. Dinkelma (2008) ascertainsthat electrification has reduced unemployment among the rural dwellers especially among women who engaged inhome made goods and services. In Pakistan, Khan and Khan (2010) discover that power shut down to textileindustries worsened unemployment,while Aqeel and Butt (2001) discover that a proper energy(electricity and gas) growth consumption policy in Pakistan would stimulate economic growth resulting inexpanded employment opportunities in the country. Statistics have shown that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) including macro-businesses are thehighest employers of labour in Nigeria (Barros, Ibiwoye & Managi, 2011). One of the major challenges ofSMEs in Nigeria is the high cost of electricity generation from private electricity power providers (Onugu,2005; Aremu & Adeyemi, 2011).The SMEs and micro-businesses (barbing and hair salons, electronic repairs, business centres, welding), in Nigeria have witnessed stunted growth due to high costs of fuel and maintenance of cost of generators. Generally, generators which are supposed to serve as backup have now become the primary source of electricity supply to industries(Okereke, 2010).

Essentially, they argue that poor budget implementations over the yearsaccount for the excruciating impacts of SMEs on the Nigerian economy, whichhas led slow growth.

Access to finance and SMEs

Many studies have performed by both foreign and local authors on the relationship between access to finance and growth of SMEs. Ohachosim (2012) carried out a study to ascertain the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria using simple percentage non-parametric technique. The result shows that despite all the efforts of government and progress attain by SMEs in Nigeria, access to finance still remain the worst among all the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria.

Aremu and Adeyemi (2011) carried a study in Nigeria to find out the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria employing ANOVA statistical technique. Their result shows that access to funds is one the major challenges facing of SMEs in Nigeria.

Akingunola (2011) performs a study on the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria using Rho spearman. The result shows that there is a positive relationship between SMEs financing and economic growth in Nigeria via investment level.

METHODOLOGY

Data source and research instrument

The sample size is be twenty (20) medium scale companies were selected from the agro allied industry, medium scale manufacturing industry, bakery, block industry and furniture industry using the judgmental and simple random sampling technique. The study used judgmental sampling technique to filter out enterprises that have less than ten employees. Two hundred copies questionnaire were administered to the selected respondents. The research instrument for this research is the Likert-type questionnaire and two way questionnaire open and closed ended questions. The open ended are multiple choice questions suitable for obtaining the respondents evaluation or assessment of an object. It indicates the extent to which respondent agree or disagree with given statement.

The close ended questions require NO or YES answer. The close ended questions also give room for respondent to answer a question from his own point view

Method of data analysis

This study use the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression technique to ascertain the relationship between access to fund and growth of SMEs. Before we analyze our statistical data, we performed some preliminary statistical test such as descriptive statistics and correlation matrix. Simple t- test was used for analyzing the questionnaire. The analysis of this research was done by the application of Microsoft excel software.

Presentation and Interpretation

Figure 1

Researcher's computation

From the analysis of the responses retrieved, of the 200 respondents whose responses were used for the analysis, figure 2 shows that 120 of the respondents were male which represents 60% of the sample while 80 of the respondents were females which represent 40% of the sample.

Figure 2

Researcher's computation 2017

From the analysis of the responses retrieved, of the 200 respondents whose responses were used for the analysis, 20 of the respondents reported that their firms do not alternative source of power e which represents 10% of the sample while 190 of the respondents which represent 90% of the sample reported that their firms have alternative sources of power supply.

Source: Researcher’s computation 2017

From the analysis of the responses retrieved, fig 3 shows , 25% of the respondents remit taxes to five difference tax agencies; 45% of the respondents report that their firms remit taxes to four different tax agencies ; 1% of the respondent reported that their firms remit taxes to three tax authorities ; 14% of the respondents reported that their firms remit taxes to two tax agencies ; and 15%of the respondents reported that their firms remit tax to one tax authority.

Table 1

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances			
	TAX	AFIN	PW

Mean	81.5	81.5	75.625
Variance	1090.857	1304.8	1960.26
Observations	8	8	8
Df	8	9	9
t Stat	5.267009	4.624476	3.053465
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.000379	0.000623	0.006858
t Critical one-tail	1.859548	1.833113	1.833113
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.000758	0.001246	0.013716
t Critical two-tail	2.306004	2.26215	2.262157

Source: Researcher’s computation 2017

TAX= Tax challenges, AFIN= Access to financial, PW= power supply

Table 1 shows that p-value for TAX one tail is 0.004, while p-value for two tail test stood at a value of 0.0008. The critical values for one tail and two tail test stood at 1.86 and 2.31 respectively. We therefore conclude that the null hypothesis could not be retained for both one and two tail test at 2.5% and 5% level of significant respectively in line with the thumb rule ($0.0003 < 0.025, 0.0007 < 0.05$). The result further shows that t-value is 5.2. This implies that double taxation is one the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria

Furthermore AFIN the result shows t-test for one tail test that p-values is 0.0006 for one tail test, while p-value for two tail test stood at a value of 0.0012. The critical for one tail and two tail test stood at 1.83 and 2.62 respectively. We therefore conclude that the null hypothesis could not be retained for both one and two tail test at 2.5% and 5% level of significant respectively in line with the thumb rule ($0.0012 < 0.025, 0.014 < 0.05$). The result further shows that t-value is 4.6. This implies that access to finance is one the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria.

Finally, the results that p-values for PW for one tail test is 0.006, while p-value for two tail test stood at a value of 0.0013. The critical for one tail and two tail test stood at 1.86 and 2.31 respectively. We therefore conclude that the null hypothesis could not be retained for both one and two tail test at 2.5% and 5% level of significant respectively in line with the thumb rule ($0.0003 < 0.025, 0.0007 < 0.05$). The result further shows that z-value is 3.1. This implies power supply is one the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria

Ranking of the challenges			
Point	Column I	Rank	Percent
PW	95	1	47.50%
FIN	84	2	42.50%
TAX	21	3	10.00%

Table 2

The challenges facing SMEs on a scale of one to three with one as the worst problem and 3 the least by the 200 respondents shows that 47.% or 95 rated power supply as the first worst problem. While 84 or 42.50% ranked the access to finance as the 2nd worst problem. Finally 21 or 10% ranked double taxation as the third worst problem,

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study was aimed at finding out the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria. The study used survey research design to gather data from the field. Questionnaire was designed to collect information from respondents in SMEs sector. The results show that tax double taxation is one the challenges facing SMEs in Nigeria. The results show that more than 80% of the respondents' firms are belaboured with payment of multiple taxation. They pay the same tax to more than one tax agent at both local and state levels. For example they are required to pay tax for sign post to the state government. Having paid this tax to state government, the local government also forcefully coerces them to pay the same tax.

The results further show that epileptic power supply with incessant outages affects the operation of SMEs in Nigeria. The results reveal that at least 10% of SMEs do not have alternative power supply. The results also suggest that intermittent power supply is a major challenge facing SMEs.

In addition, the results shows that access to finance is a major challenge that hampers the growth of SMEs in Nigeria. The study reveals that high interest rate and the inability to offer collateral are largely responsible for the banks' inability to approve many loan requests made by SMEs.

Finally, the result shows the challenges facing SMEs on a scale of one to three ranked inadequate power supply number one worst problem, the access to finance as the 2nd worst problem and ranked double taxation as the third worst problem,

This study recommended that commercial banks should reduce credit allocation requirements in terms of collateral and interest in order to increase credit allocation to SMEs to enhance economic growth in Nigeria. This study further recommended tax incentive should be given to SMEs. Finally, government should increase power generation to enhance productivity of SMEs

Limitations of study

There are some factors or constraints that hinder the researcher in achieving the whole intention of this work. Scarcity of data and response of response to questions. The limitation is paucity of literature on the subject. These challenges notwithstanding, the research is still very valid and empirical.

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APPENDIX

QUESTIONIARE

Section A

Instruction: Tick as Appropriate

1. Whichgroup do you belong toBakery Block industry Furniture industry
2. Gender Male , Female
3. Do have alternative source of power supply in your firm Yes No , 50 and above
4. How many agencies do you pay taxes to? A. Above three B Not less than three C Above two D.One

Section B

	Taxation	SA	A	UD	SD	DA	TOTAL
5	Paying a particular level twice affects the survival medium scale firm	102	80	0	10	8	200
6	Multiple taxation constitute affect SMEs' profitability	121	40	0	20	19	200
7	Tax rate put disproportionate pressure on SME	98	50	0	32	20	200
8	Tax administration poses challenges on SMEs growth	117	44	0	21	18	200
	Power supply						
10	Cost of running generator affects the	102	49	0	45	4	200

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>TAX</i>	<i>CH</i>	
Mean	81.5	FIN18.5	<i>CH</i>
Variance	1090.857	53.81429	18.625
Observations	200	1304.8570	173.9821
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	200	200
Df	8	9	
t Stat	5.267009	4.624476	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.000379	0.000623	
t Critical one-tail	1.859548	1.833113	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.000758	0.001246	
t Critical two-tail		2.262157	
t Critical two-tail	2.306004		

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>PW</i>	<i>CH</i>
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Mean	75.625	24.375
Variance	1960.268	293.4107
Observations	200	200
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	9	
t Stat	3.053465	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.006858	
t Critical one-tail	1.833113	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.013716	
t Critical two-tail	2.262157	

<i>Point</i>	<i>Column1</i>	<i>Rank</i>	<i>Percent</i>
2	95	1	100.00%
3	84	2	50.00%
1	21	3	0.00%